
197. The Gaia Sausage-Enceladus stream

THE TOPIC of stellar streams, key in understanding the Milky Way's formation, has been transformed by Gaia. I have written several essays on them already: the Enceladus stream (essay 15), other stream discoveries (71 and 156), and their use as probes of black holes (176) and Λ CDM-type sub-halos (184). More than 100 are now known, and in this and the following two essays, I will focus on three of them: Enceladus, Sagittarius, and Cetus.

IN ESSAY 15 (April 2021) I gave a top-level picture of what was called the 'Enceladus' stream in the discovery paper by Helmi et al. (2018), and which was described as 'sausage-shaped' in velocity-space in the independent discovery paper(s) by Belokurov et al. (2018) and Myeong et al. (2018). It is now known as the Gaia Sausage-Enceladus, or GSE, stream. It is not, let me note, the same as the 'Helmi stream', discovered in the Hipparcos data by Helmi et al. (1999).

Refereed papers mentioning GSE in their *abstract* is rising: 10 in 2019, 25 in 2020, 35 in 2021, 40 in 2022, 40 in 2023, and 30 so far in 2024. This underscores the stream's importance in revealing the assembly history of the Milky Way – structurally, dynamically, and chemically, and its use as a Rosetta Stone for understanding our Galaxy's formation in a cosmological context.

I will give only some key points in our understanding of the GSE stream, and keep the detailed discovery steps, and references, to a minimum. The pre-Gaia understanding of the Galaxy's halo and its formation, and much more on what is known about GSE, can be found in the recent review by Deason & Belokurov (2024).

OVER THE PAST 20–30 years, through a combination of observations, theory, and simulations, aided by N-body simulations of the large-scale structure of the Λ CDM Universe, it became clear that the halo should be the graveyard of many other galaxies, gravitationally captured by the Milky Way galaxy over its lifetime, as in [this animation](#). Dynamical timescales in the outer halo are longer than the age of the Universe, so it should preserve a fossil record of these ancient encounters.

OVER BILLIONS of years, galaxies gravitationally captured by the Milky Way slowly spiral inwards, the more distant (Sagittarius and the Magellanic Clouds) showing only early signs of capture and disruption, the most ancient on their second or subsequent orbital approach. While they steadily dissolve in 6D phase-space, i.e. progressively scattering through the halo in terms of their positions and velocities, some preserve clear signatures of their common origin through a clustering of their abundance patterns *and* their orbital properties.

More precisely, while they may be widely scattered on the sky, their common origin is encoded in their similar 'integrals of motion', e.g. in their total energy, E_{tot} , and their projected orbital angular momentum (Helmi & de Zeeuw, 2000; Binney & Tremaine, 2008, §3.1.1).

THERE IS NOT SPACE here to elaborate on the many post-discovery studies of the GSE stream which have been piecing together its properties, dynamics and origin, nor on the many other halo streams that have now been identified with Gaia ([Galstreams](#) lists 126 tracks, in 95 distinct stellar streams, as of March 2022).

But I will pick out the study by Naidu et al. (2020), where some of their conclusions were particularly striking, and which serves as a context. They used 5684 giants with distances $|Z| > 2$ kpc from the Galactic plane, combining spectroscopy and radial velocities from the MMT-H3 survey with Gaia DR2 astrometry, and they identified several clear clusterings in terms of their chemistry ($[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}]$), and their position in energy-angular momentum space, $E_{\text{tot}} - L_z$.

They identified various prominent structures and streams already reported in previous studies, viz. the high- α disk, the *in situ* halo, the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy, along with the GSE, Helmi, Sequoia, and Thamnos streams. They also identified four other streams (both prograde and retrograde) with distinct chemistries and orbits: Aleph, Arjuna, I'toi and Wukong. The top left figure (over) shows all these clusterings, also distinguishing those on radial orbits ($J_z < J_R$, normal font) from those on polar, circular orbits ($J_z > J_R$, italic font).

THE GSE MERGER, some ~ 9.5 Gyr ago (at $z \lesssim 3$), had a major effect on the halo. Naidu et al. (2020) found that, at $|Z| \gtrsim 15$ kpc, the debris of just two massive accreted dwarfs ($10^8 - 10^9 M_\odot$) comprise 80% of the halo, together explaining the relatively high overall halo metallicity, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] \approx -1.2$. They attributed 95% of their sample to one of their dozen identified structures (their inferred composition versus Z is shown, above right), pointing to a halo built *entirely* from accreted dwarfs.

Within 25 kpc, GSE, with $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.2$, was a radial merger that now dominates the local metal-poor halo. The ‘head-on’ collision resulted in rapid phase mixing, evident today only in its clustered integrals of motion.

Beyond 25 kpc, the halo is dominated by the Sagittarius (Sgr) dwarf galaxy and stream, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -1.0$, one of the first identified halo streams (Ibata et al., 1994). Here, both the residual galaxy core, as well as two vast preceding and trailing streams, are clearly discernable.

Later simulations by Naidu et al. (2021) suggest a GSE mass at infall of $5 \times 10^8 M_\odot$ in stars and $2 \times 10^{11} M_\odot$ in dark matter, that it arrived on a retrograde orbit, with Arjuna being its retrograde debris, and Sequoia and I’toi perhaps also being stripped from its outer regions.

MERGERS ALSO HAVE a significant effect on the disk, a prominent example being the Gaia phase-space spiral, or ‘snail’, attributed to phase-mixing through past pericentric passage of the Sgr dwarf (Antoja et al., 2018).

A major local disk component is the ‘high- α disk’ and its high-eccentricity tail (or ‘*in situ* halo’), comprising some 15% of the local Galaxy. Naidu et al. (2021) argued that the continuous eccentricity distribution supports a picture in which a primordial high- α disk was disturbed and ‘heated’, possibly by the GSE merger. A similar origin was attributed to the ‘splash’ population (Belokurov et al., 2020; Deason & Belokurov, 2024, §4.2).

But studies are still ongoing, and involve the footprints of past mergers in the form of ‘energy wrinkles’ and ‘phase-space folds’ (aka chevrons or caustics). While Belokurov et al. (2023) again attributed these to the GSE merger, other much younger events have also left their own mixed contributions (e.g. Donlon et al., 2022; Donlon & Newberg, 2023; Donlon et al., 2024).

THE DEMONSTRATED correlation between the combined mass of a galaxy’s globular clusters and its total mass (e.g. Dorman & Harris, 2023) implies that while many tidal debris remnants are expected to be detected in the stellar halo, only the most massive would be accompanied by globular clusters on similar orbits. This opens up another fascinating aspect of the properties and origin of the many halo streams now known.

In the case of GSE, Myeong et al. (2018) showed that amongst our Galaxy’s *accreted* clusters, a tight grouping have very similar orbital actions (with small pericentres $\lesssim 2$ kpc, and large apocentres $\gtrsim 10$ kpc), consistent with clusters associated with the GSE merger event.

TO CONCLUDE this outline, I refer again to Deason & Belokurov (2024) for a more detailed discussion of the progenitor mass, the event timing, the effects on our Galaxy disk, and the implications for understanding the ongoing Sagittarius and Magellanic Cloud mergers.

And I should also stress that the large-scale Λ CDM-based simulations of structure formation are also guiding interpretation, and providing support, to the picture of Milky Way-type galaxies which have undergone major GSE-like mergers (e.g. Renaud et al., 2021; Sestito et al., 2021; Dillamore et al., 2022; Khoperskov et al., 2023; Orkney et al., 2023; Semenov et al., 2024).

THERE IS much more that we would like to know, and future Gaia releases should provide much greater clarity, and many more answers.

Deason & Belokurov (2024) concluded their review with a number of open questions, amongst them:

- * does the luminosity function of destroyed dwarfs down to low masses agree with the Λ CDM predictions?
- * how instrumental was GSE in the Galaxy’s evolution: when did it merge, how much material did it bring, and how does it link to the disk, bulge, and bar formation?
- * why did the disk form so early, and is this reproducible in cosmological simulations?
- * what is the origin of the stellar halo spin, and does this relate to the spinning up of the Milky Way disk?
- * what happened to the satellites associated with the pre-infall massive dwarf galaxies like the GSE?